

Speculation of the Relationship of Spin to Rotational Invariance Part 2

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In Part 1, we considered a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle, i.e. one with rest mass, and tried to argue that there may be rotational invariance even without usual angular momentum, i.e. rotational motion of the full system. In other words, physically it seems that some partial angular type motion, not necessarily linked to 360 degrees may be stirred up. In particular, we argued for rotational invariance in a plane perpendicular to each axis. We then noted that rotational invariance is broken due to the possibility of two directions of circling the axis. This leads to chunkiness or two spin projections. We noted that the 2x2 Pauli matrix operators of these two degrees of motion allow one to write: $\sum_i p_i s_i = B$ such that $B^2 = p \cdot p$. This $p \cdot p$ expression is part of $E^2 = c^2 p \cdot p + m_0^2 c^4$, i.e. an equation with m_0 which does not allow one to remove the dot product as can be done if $m_0=0$ (i.e. $E = |p|c$).

Here, we consider the case of a photon and note that one physically has rotation of the entire electric E and magnetic fields B (and hence entire energy density) about the axis of momentum in the case of circularly polarized electric and magnetic fields. Thus, the photon situation is a little different than that of a rest mass, because even though one has $(p(x), p(y), p(z))$, one does not have rotational invariance about all three axes independently, but only about the axis of the p vector due to the restriction of energy to a plane perpendicular to p . The notion of rotational invariance about a certain axis (p vector axis) exists, but not about the x, y, z axes.

We try to argue then that this rotational invariance is linked with energy considerations. In the case of a photon, the electric and magnetic fields must lie in a plane perpendicular to the momentum vector. There is an energy restriction linked with a particular axis. In the case of rest mass, there is no such restriction. Energy exists as rest mass if there is no momentum. If there is momentum, it seems one must consider rotational invariance about all three axes (if one considers it at all). This leads to the difference in the idea of spin in the rest mass and photon cases, we argue, but both are linked with rotational invariance about one or more axes. For a photon, one has symmetry breaking (i.e. two directions of motion about the p axis), but given that energy lies in this plane can be circularly polarized, one may actually have physical angular momentum representing spin. In the rest mass case, one has no such situation, although it seems that some partial angular type of motion may occur to create a type of current which interacts with a magnetic field. Thus, it seems that rotational invariance is linked with energy considerations as well as spin.

Part 1

In Part 1, we considered a particle with rest mass and momentum vector p , and argued that there should be rotational invariance about each axis, even if there is not overall angular momentum. In particular, a particle with rest mass m_0 at rest has no angular momentum, and if it is made to move in one direction, there is no overall angular momentum of the entire energy. That does not preclude, however, partial angular types of motion if one suggests rotational invariance about each axis. We note that each $p(i)$ (p_x, p_y, p_z) is linked with a probability $\exp(-i p(i) x_i)$ which introduces a chunkiness in space. $\exp(-i p(i) x_i)$ is a probability and must have the

same value for $p(i) \rightarrow -p(i)$ and $x_i \rightarrow -x_i$. This seems to be the driver of the chunkiness, along with the periodicity of the function required to create a semblance of spatial invariance. This leads to the suggestion that one might consider rotational invariance (just like translational invariance for $\exp(ipx)$ about each axis and impose a chunkiness due to the possibility of motion in two directions about each axis. This chunkiness breaks invariance, but is linked with a conserved quantity, the z component of spin. This is not overall angular momentum of the whole system, but a kind of partial angular momentum it seems which exists and allows for interaction with a magnetic field.

Given that there is a rest mass which does not show preference to any axis, one may impose the condition of rotational invariance about each axis. Thus, one has a chunkiness of two eigenfunctions (1,0), (0,1) about each axis. The set of 2x2 matrices linked with this scenario allow one to write;

$$P \cdot p = (\sum \text{over } i \ p_i \ s_i) (\sum \text{over } i \ p_i \ s_i) \quad ((1a))$$

This focus on $p \cdot p$ is only relevant, however, because $p \cdot p$ appears in:

$$-EE = c^2 p \cdot p + m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((1b))$$

If $m_0=0$, one may actually remove the $p \cdot p$ and obtain $E=|p|c$. Thus, it is the rest mass m_0 , which forces one to retain $p \cdot p$. This allows one to consider rotation about each axis such that the operators (2x2 Pauli matrices) can enforce $p \cdot p$ when p vector is written as:

$$(\sum \text{over } i \ p_i \ s_i) W \quad \text{where } W \text{ is the wavefunction} \quad ((1c))$$

The Photon Situation

A photon also has a p vector and one might suggest, based on the above, that it too should have rotational invariance about each axis. The photon, however, differs from a particle with rest mass in a fundamental way. The energy is directly linked with the momentum vector. In other words, the p vector is one direction and the electric and magnetic fields lie in a plane perpendicular to p . The energy density is thus constrained to a plane perpendicular to motion:

$$\text{Energy density} = .5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } E \text{ and } B \text{ are the electric and magnetic field} \quad ((2))$$

This is not the case for a particle with rest mass, which has mass associated with all three axes. Thus, we suggest that for a photon, one should only consider rotational invariance about the p axis. It is interesting, however, that one may actually see this motion because of the E, B field plane. In this case, if one has circularly polarized electric and magnetic fields, the entire energy density is associated with rotational motion and this is not some kind of partial angular type motion, but actual usual overall angular momentum. Thus, the photon case is different from that of a particle with rest mass.

In the rest mass case, we noted how the Pauli 2x2 matrices allow one to create $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, but ultimately one deals with 4x4 Dirac matrices in $-EE = c\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} + m_0 c^2$ with $E \rightarrow i \frac{d}{dt}$ partial and $\mathbf{p} \rightarrow -i \text{grad}$ partial. As a result, one sees clearly the restriction of rest mass in this equation and the rotational invariance about each axis which creates $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ is also part of the overall equation containing m_0 . As a result, one cannot make a $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ argument for Pauli matrices alone, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that just as momentum represents chunkiness which breaks spatial invariance for $p(x)$, $p(y)$, $p(z)$, there should be rotational invariance about each axis if there is a rest mass. A rest mass ensures that there is energy linked with all three axes, even if there is a preferred direction, namely the \mathbf{p} vector direction. There is still energy. and so rotational invariance, about the other axes, with no special bias for the \mathbf{p} direction because spin magnitude is not a function of the magnitude of \mathbf{p} . As a result, one may choose an axis (e.g. the z axis) and write two spinors (1,0) and (0,1) representing angular type motion in two directions. This breaks rotational invariance and leads to chunkiness (just like the chunkiness of a wavelength). These two spinors are eigenfunctions of the 2x2 s_z Pauli matrix and one may obtain the other Pauli matrices such that: $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} = (\sum \text{over } i p_i s_i) (\sum \text{over } i p_i s_i)$. This operation may be considered because it is linked with the equation $-EE = c\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} + m_0 c^2$. In other words, rest mass appears in the above equation and it is only this case that one considers the 2x2 Pauli matrices.

A photon also has a \mathbf{p} vector and one might suggest rotational invariance about the $p(i)$ axis. The problem is that there is no initial energy which may be linked to all three axes, but only energy due to the electric and magnetic fields in a plane perpendicular to the \mathbf{p} vector. Thus, there is only one kind of rotational invariance in the photon case, linked to motion about the \mathbf{p} vector. If the electric and magnetic fields are circularly polarized, then they rotate about the \mathbf{p} vector and given that energy density = $.5 \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + .5/\mu_0 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$, one has actual full angular momentum of the entire energy, not some partial angular type motion as in the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ rest mass case, we argue. Again, the magnitude of spin is fixed (1 for the photon), but there are still two chunky pieces $m=1$ or $m=-1$ associated with motion in two directions. $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$ is no longer part of a constraint equation as one has $E=pc$, i.e one may eliminate $\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p}$, something one cannot do for $-EE = c\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} + m_0 c^2$ (without linearizing and introducing 4x4 matrices).